

METHODS OF USING MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING IN STUDENTS

Sultonova L.B.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: l.sultonova@bk.ru

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Abstract: This article discusses the fact that the process of developing students' creative abilities consists of theoretically developed didactic approaches, the tasks performed in this process, the principles that are important to follow in increasing efficiency, and the stages of their implementation.

Keywords: emotional-psychic, innovative technologies, psycho-individual characteristics, intellectual abilities, logical reasoning, creative approach, creative imagination, imagination, architecture, emotional factor The development of creative abilities in students requires, first of all, a person-oriented approach, emotional-psychic mood, active, creative imagination, self-activation, independence, self-control, manifestation, expression, evaluation, the use of innovative educational technologies in the educational process. Abilities are considered a set of mental individual characteristics that allow acquiring important knowledge, skills and qualifications for productive activity.

Creative imagination is the ability of a person to suddenly embody or deliberately create images, symbols, objects of ideas in his mind, an integral component of productive thinking. The emotional-volitional characteristics of a person depend on his intellectual-creative abilities. Memory (which takes on a specific, specific form in accordance with the requirements of the activity), emotionality, that is, susceptibility to emotions - this feature can be considered as auxiliary features that increase the activity of a person. "One of the most important social qualities that manifests professional qualities in students is creativity. The concept of creativity is a process that expresses the creative potential of the student's personality, as well as his independence.

Creativity is directly related to thinking, in which quality and quantity are manifested. Student creativity is an activity based on the creative understanding of the specific essence of events and phenomena. Convergent thinking is aimed at a previously known trivial solution to the problem. Divergent thinking is manifested when the problem has not yet been identified, there is no previously proposed, established method of solving it. Creativity is an aspect related to the intellectual potential of the student's personality, which develops with creativity in thinking and creative cooperation in the learning process. It is desirable to ensure a more open approach to teaching and learning in the development of student creativity, attitudes and behavior.

Therefore, in the formation of creative skills in students, it is important to create pedagogical situations that are conducive to the development of their creativity and abilities. Due to the lack of creative qualities of the teacher, students also have interesting and wonderful ideas, but they are slow to express them. Therefore, without a deep understanding of the individual aspects and the entire mechanism of pedagogical creativity, it is impossible to effectively develop it in the system of continuous education.